

Synthesis of Magnetic Nanocrystals by Thermal Decomposition in Glycol Media: Effect of Process Variables and Mechanistic Study

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ABSTRACT

The nucleation and growth of water dispersible iron-oxide nanoparticles synthesized by high temperature decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate in the presence of different solvents has been studied. A battery of techniques was used to characterize the products obtained under different conditions and to elucidate the synthesis mechanism. Results show that the synthesis of iron-oxide nanoparticles in triethylene glycol (TEG) proceeds through a multistep process whose first stage is likely to be the formation of an intermediate TEG-iron-complex that evolves into a low-crystallinity iron-oxide-organic precursor during aging at 180 °C. Raising the temperature above 240 °C caused the thermal decomposition of the precursor and the sudden nucleation of small iron-oxide nanocrystals. Keeping the reactant mixture at 280 °C led to the growth of iron-oxide nanocrystals, as did increasing the time at reflux temperature, the amount of initial iron precursor or the use high boiling point solvents. The particle size could be reproducibly controlled between 1.5 and 13 nm, with a relatively narrow size distribution. Larger particles could also be obtained using a solvothermal method in an autoclave reactor.

INTRODUCTION

Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs), such as magnetite (Fe_3O_4) or maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), represent a versatile class of biocompatible nanoplateforms, able to combine diagnosis and therapeutic functionalities^[1,2]. Because of this, colloidal dispersions of SPIONs are being actively investigated in a variety of fields in nanomedicine including advanced magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), drug delivery, magnetic hyperthermia, tissue engineering, and bisoseparation^[3-7].

A widespread use of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles in clinical applications would require scalable and standardized synthesis methods, leading to the mass production of SPIONs with high purity, monodispersity, reproducible batch-to-batch characteristics, and good stability under storage. Nowadays, dispersions of SPIONs are commercially synthesized by co-precipitation of Fe(II) and Fe(III) salts in the presence of an appropriate macromolecule that provides a hydrophilic coating, rendering the nanoparticles water soluble and stable^[8,9]. However, coprecipitation methods have proven notoriously difficult to control, often leading to significant variability in nanoparticle size, dispersity and magnetic properties. An additional problem is the long-term stability of the coating on the nanoparticle surface which is often lost with storage time or with changes to the dilution or the ionic strength of the medium, leading to particle agglomeration.

These problems have prompted the investigation of alternative synthesis procedures including gas phase (laser-induced pyrolysis)^[10,11], and gas/aerosol methods (spray pyrolysis)^[12], laser ablation^[13], arc discharge^[14], solvated-metal-atom-dispersion^[15], sonolysis^[16], microwave irradiation^[17], templated crystal growth^[18], hydrothermal methods^[19], electrochemical methods^[20], microemulsion methods^[21], nonhydrolytic sol-gel

processes^[22-24], and thermal decomposition of metallic precursors in a variety of scenarios^[25-29]. This work investigates the latter group, since these methods seem to represent the best approach for the fabrication of SPIONs with excellent crystallinity and a precise control of the shape and particle size.

Thermal decomposition of metalorganic precursors is frequently carried out in a hot organic solvent containing surfactants (alkylamines and carboxylic acid), which help to control particle growth and prevent particle aggregation, and a reactant that acts as reducing agent^[30]. As examples, *Sun et al.*^[27,28] have reported the synthesis of ferrite nanoparticles starting from their corresponding acetylacetonates in the presence of phenylether, oleic acid, oleylamine and 1,2-hexadecanediol, and *Vargas et al.*^[31] synthesized directly Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with particle sizes ranging from 4 to 12 nm through the modification of the organic solvent and by seed-mediated growth. In spite of the excellent results achieved in terms of size control and colloidal stability, a major handicap of this synthesis method for biomedical applications is the fact that particles are coated with hydrophobic surfactants. This means that a surface exchange reaction is needed to obtain water-dispersible nanoparticles. In addition, the use of toxic solvents and surfactants lowers the biocompatibility of the final products.

To overcome these limitations, *Gao and coworkers*^[32] employed organic solvents with high polarity, acting simultaneously as reducing and capping agents and providing enough hydrophilicity to make the particle suspension stable in water. Other authors have followed similar synthetic routes employing solvents such as ethylene glycol (EG), diethylene glycol (DEG), triethylene glycol (TEG), tetraethylene glycol (TTEG), 2-acetyl pyridine, p-anisaldehyde, ethylene carbonate and carboxylic acids^[29,33-35].

Despite the studies mentioned above, this synthetic route is still relatively novel, and many aspects of the mechanism involved remain unknown. In particular, the effect of the different process parameters on the average particle size, the width of the particle size distribution and the crystallinity of the synthesized SPIONs is far from established. These features are critical in many applications of SPIONs such as superparamagnetic contrast agents in MRI^[36], and as heating sources for magnetic hyperthermia^[37].

In this work we attempt to contribute to a better understanding of this important synthesis by carrying out a systematic study of a representative system for the preparation of water dispersible SPIONs: the thermal decomposition of iron acetyl acetonate [Fe(acac)₃] in the presence of TEG and other polyalcohols. In doing so, we explored the effect of the main process parameters on the final size, dispersity and magnetic properties of the as-obtained water dispersible SPIONs. Particle nucleation and growth processes have been followed by drawing aliquots at different synthesis times, which were subjected to a thorough characterization using a battery of instrumental techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Nanoparticle Synthesis

Nanoparticle synthesis experiments were carried out using commercial available analytical grade reagents without further purification. Absolute ethanol, ethylene glycol (EG, ≥99% purity), diethylene glycol (DEG, ≥99%), triethylene glycol (TEG, 99%), tetraethylene glycol (TTEG, 99%), trioctylamine (TOA, 98%), trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO, 99%), ethyl acetate, and iron(III) acetylacetonate [Fe(acac)₃] (≥97%) were purchased from Sigma-

Aldrich. The composition of the physiological buffer (PBS) used is 0.01 M phosphate buffer in a 0.8% saline solution (137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl).

Water dispersible superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles were synthesized as described by *Cai et al.*^[29], with some modifications described next. The main stages in the synthesis process are shown in Scheme 1. The *standard synthesis conditions* were defined as follows: 200 mg of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ and 30 mL of triethylene glycol were mixed in a three neck flask and heated at 15 °C/min, to 180°C (point N1 in Scheme 1), a temperature close to the decomposition temperature of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ (180 °C ~ 190 °C). The reaction was kept at this temperature for 30 minutes in order to induce decomposition of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ precursor (point N2) and then heated again at 5 °C/min to reach the boiling temperature of the solvent used (point N3, corresponding to 558 K for the standard conditions, when TEG was used as a solvent). The reacting mixture was kept under reflux for a certain period (30 min for standard conditions) until the end of the reaction time (point N4), and then cooled to room temperature. After reaction the particles were washed with a mixture of ethyl acetate and ethanol and separated using a magnet. The washing cycle was repeated 3 times and then the nanoparticles were successfully transferred to water or to Phosphate Buffered Saline solution (PBS), producing a highly stable aqueous suspension of magnetic nanoparticles and dialyzed during 2 days. This sample will be termed TEG-SPION.

Scheme 1. Main stages and parameters in the synthesis process.

To explore the effect of the process parameters involved in the polyol-mediated synthesis on the final structural properties, a matrix of synthesis experiments was designed in which the value of one of the synthesis parameters was changed in each run, the rest being kept at their standard values unless otherwise indicated. Table 1 gives the parameters studied and their values.

Characterization

Phase identification of SPIONs was performed by using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The XRD patterns were recorded between 5° and 90° (2θ) at $2^\circ/\text{min}$ in a Rigaku/Max System diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm). Crystalline size was calculated from the broadening of the (311) reflection using Debye-Scherrer's equation^[38]. The shape, size, particle size distribution and microstructure of the iron oxide nanocrystals were studied by using a T200 Philips Tecnai Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) operated at 200 kV. At least one hundred nanoparticles were measured to evaluate the mean diameter of the particles and the standard deviation. The data were fitted with a log-normal distribution function and the logarithmic standard deviation was obtained for all the

samples Hydrodynamic sizes were evaluated in a 90 Plus dynamic light scattering (DLS) apparatus (Brookhaven). A TGA/SDTA 851 Mettler Toledo thermobalance was used to study the thermal decomposition of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ in the solid state. The products of the thermal decomposition of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ in polyol were monitorized *on line* by using a quadrupole mass spectrometer Pfeiffer Vacuum Thermostar GSD301T and *off line* by Ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (Jasco V670). The magnetic behavior of the reaction mixture sampled at different reaction times was studied in a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID), model SQUID MPM-55S Quantum Design. Magnetization curves were obtained out at 5 K applying a maximum field of 5 T and in the RSO mode. Diamagnetic contributions coming from the sample holder and solvent were subtracted from the curves.

Parameter tested	
Heating rate to 180 °C β_1 (°C/min)	5, 10, 15
Aging time at 180 °C (min)	5, 30 , 60
Heating rate to reflux β_2 (°C/min)	2, 5 , 10
Reflux time (min)	5, 30 , 60
Mass of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ (g)	0.05, 0.2 , 0.4, 1.3, 2, 3
Solvent used	EG ^[39] , DEG ^[39] , TEG ^[39] , TTEG ^[40] , TEG/TOA ^[41] , TEG/TOPO ^[42]
Final temperature (°C)	197, 245, 254, 280 , 315, 365

Table 1. Physical parameters studied and modified values compared to the standard synthesis. Data in bold type represents standard synthesis parameters.

RESULTS

Synthesis under standard conditions

Synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles using standard conditions leads to a stable suspension of magnetic nanocrystals. The X-ray diffraction pattern of a typical as-obtained sample is shown in figure 1.a. The positions and intensities of the peaks are coincident with the XRD pattern for a bulk magnetite phase with cubic inverse spinel structure (Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) card number 89-0691). The lattice parameter of this material calculated from the position of the (311) peak was approximately 8.36 Å, which could be associated with magnetite (8.39 Å) or maghemite (8.33 - 8.39 Å). Since the particles are finally stabilized in water (high O₂ solubility) and have a small size (most of the Fe atoms are located at the surface), the existence of a solid solution between the two phases cannot be excluded. An average crystallite size of 7 nm was obtained from the (311) reflection, which is similar to that found by TEM (see below) indicating that particles are highly crystalline and are single crystals.

Figure 1.b presents a representative TEM micrograph of the magnetite nanoparticles dispersed in water. The synthesized SPIONs were of a roughly spherical morphology, uniform in size and quasi-non-aggregated in water. Figure 1.c displays a representative particle size distribution determined by the analysis of TEM micrographs. The obtained particle size distribution was fitted to a log-normal distribution function, with a size of 5 ± 2 (standard deviation) nm. Analysis of the Fourier transform power spectrum (insert in figure 1.d) allowed to determine lattice fringe spaces of approximately 4.84 Å, 2.96 Å and 2.53 Å, which are close to the expected lattice fringes for the (111), (220) and (311) planes of an inverse cubic spinel structure type magnetite or maghemite in agreement with the results obtained by XRD.

The average hydrodynamic size (D_H) of the particles for a colloidal dispersion of TEG coated-SPIONs in a phosphate buffered saline solution (PBS) was 16 ± 2 nm. Since the particle size measured by TEM is considerably smaller (~ 5 nm) this would indicate that TEG-coated SPIONs form stable colloidal aggregates of around 30 particles in PBS. However, the naked particle size determined by TEM is not representative of the hydrodynamic size, since the surface coating of the particle and the water molecules that are hydrogen bonded to that coating contribute to a larger effective size. Therefore, the 16 nm colloidal aggregates probably include a smaller number of particles.

Effect of process parameters.

Once reproducible results had been achieved under standard conditions, the effect of the different variables was studied, with the values given in table 1. The TEM analysis of representative TEG coated-SPIONs synthesized with different heating rates from 25 °C to 180 °C and from 180 °C to 280 °C (see supporting information, figures S1 and S2) revealed the different heating rates used produced negligible variations on the mean particle size of these samples. The slight variations on the particle size distribution observed are not considered significant because they were within the expected margin of error of the imaging software used to analyze these micrographs.

Figure 1. Structural Characterization of TEG-coated iron oxide particles obtained under standard conditions: a) XRD pattern (the reflections of Fe_3O_4 were included for comparison); b) TEM micrograph of iron oxide nanoparticles; c) Particle size distribution calculated from analysis of TEM images (lognormal curve fitting) and d) Lattice plane fringes and Fourier transform of the indicated zone of the particles.

Similarly, the data obtained (see supporting information, figure S3) showed that increasing the aging time at 180°C from 5 to 60 min did not change significantly the average particle size and particle size distribution of the obtained SPIONs. On the other hand, the modification of the time at reflux (280°C) from 5 to 30 min brought along a clear increase of the particle size from 3 to 5 nm (see information, figure S4), which suggested that growth of the particles took place during reflux time. However, an additional increase of the time to 60 min did not cause a further modification of the particle size.

The $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ concentration in the reactant mixture was found to be an important synthetic parameter regarding the particle size of the as-synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles. TEM images of particles synthesized by using different concentration of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ are shown in Figure 2. It was found that the increase of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ amount in

the reactant solution from 0.05 g to 3 g continuously increased the mean particle size from 4 to around 12 nm. At the same time, the average aggregate size in PBS measured by DLS (data not shown) increased from 15 nm to 60 nm indicating that aggregates now contain roughly 4 times more particles, compared to the SPIONs obtained under standard conditions.

Recent studies of thermal decomposition of metal precursors in a solution containing capping ligands have demonstrated that the choice of appropriate solvents and surfactants is crucially important in order to control the characteristics of the produced nanocrystals^[43-45]. In this work, SPIONs syntheses were also conducted in a variety of solvents with different viscosities and boiling points, such as EG, DEG, and TTEG. Also, mixtures containing equal volume mixtures of TEG/Trioctylamine and TTEG/Trioctylphosphine oxide were also as solvents. While the standard values were used for heating rates and reflux times, the reflux temperature could be increased from 197 °C to 365 °C as a function of the boiling point of the solvents used. The boiling points of each of the solvents used and their viscosity values are given in table 2.

Figure 2. TEM images and particle size distributions of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized using different amount of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$: a) 0.05 g, b) 0.2 g, c) 0.4 g, d) 1.3 g, e) 2 g and f) 3 g.

Figure 3 shows the TEM images of SPIONs prepared by using solvents with different boiling points. It can be clearly seen that the particle size increased with the boiling point of the solvent, which determined the temperature of the final reaction stage. When EG was used as solvent, the sample seemed to be formed by very small particles ($\sim 1\text{-}2$ nm in size) of a material with poor crystallinity. Since the reflux temperature used in this experiment, $197\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, was close to the decomposition temperature of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ ($180\text{-}190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), and given the fact that, as shown below, this material did not show any significant response under the influence of an external magnetic field, the formation of a intermediate metal

complex, such as alkoxy-acetylacetonate Fe^{3+} could not be excluded, although the very small size of these particles makes it difficult to determine the exact nature of the material.

SOLVENT [ref]	EG [38]	DEG [38]	TEG [38]	TTEG [39]	TOA [40]	TOPO [41]
Boiling Point/°C	197	245	280	315	365	315
Absolute viscosity at [temperature] (mPa.s)	19.1 [22.4°C]	35.1 [21.1°C]	35.1 [26.5°C]	58.3 [25°C]	8.33 [25 °C]	1.18 [20 °C]
Absolute viscosity at boiling point (mPa.s)*	0.037	0.014	0.023	0.009	-	-

Table 2. Main characteristics of the solvents used. * Calculated using Aspen Hysys™ v7.0

On the contrary, figure 3.d indicates that the use of TTEG, the solvent with highest boiling point tested (b. p. 315 °C), favored the formation of larger iron oxide nanoparticles, which almost doubled the size of the particles synthesized by using TEG as solvent (Fig. 3.c). However, an increase of the standard deviation of the particle size distribution can also be observed. In addition, the corresponding TEM pictures (3d to 3f) clearly show some agglomeration, which may be caused by a certain degree of interparticle growth taking place at high temperatures. Finally, some experiments were carried out with TEG and TTEG, keeping the final temperature fixed at 254 °C. TEM analysis of these samples (not shown) indicates that the decrease of the final reaction temperature resulted in a significant decrease (around 20 %) of the mean particle size of the obtained SPIONs.

It is interesting to note that the use of low-viscosity, high-boiling point alkylamine (TOA) and alkylphosphine (TOPO) capping-ligands mixed with TEG and TTEG yielded large and quasi-faceted nanoparticles with larger particle size than those synthesized using pure polyol media. This is in agreement with the broad trends previously reported by *Sun et*

al.^[28] and *Cai and Wan*^[29] on the thermally induced decomposition of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ in presence of polar and non-polar solvents.

Figure 3. TEM pictures and particle size distributions of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized using different solvents: a) EG b) DEG c) TEG d) TTEG e) 1:1 vol/vol TEG/TOA mixture and f) 1:1 vol/vol TEG/TOPO mixture

Finally, some experiments were run at higher temperature by carrying out the synthesis inside an autoclave under autogenous pressure. Again, this higher temperature caused an increase of the solubility and reactivity of the metal precursors as well as a strong decrease of the viscosity of the solvents. These solvothermal experiments were performed under standard conditions but setting the temperature at 300 °C and in some cases increasing the reflux time to five hours in order to force reaction completion.

Figure 4. a) TEM images of TEG-coated SPIONs obtained by solvothermally synthesis with aging time of 30 min; b) Same as sample (a) but using aging time 5 h; c) TEM picture of particles obtained using standard conditions; d) XRD patterns of solvothermally synthesized particles, aging time 30 min (reference of bulk magnetite and iron oxide nanoparticles obtained using standard conditions are included for comparison).

Figures 4.a and 4.b display TEM pictures of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized through the use of this solvothermal route. From these images, it can be seen that 10 ± 2 nm particles have been obtained (in good agreement with XRD crystallite size of 10 nm), doubling the size of those obtained using standard conditions. Moreover, TEM analysis showed that the

average size increased with aging time, in accordance with the results already described for conventional synthesis. However, some inter-particle necks began to emerge, as shows in figure 4b, leading to agglomeration of the nanoparticles. Figure 4.d shows the XRD pattern of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized by solvothermal approach. Unlike the particles obtained by conventional synthesis, this XRD pattern could be assigned to a phase of magnetite, because the lattice parameter was around 8.41 Å. This suggests an improvement in the crystallinity for the samples obtained solvothermally.

Analysis of samples at different reaction stages

To investigate the reaction mechanism sample aliquots were drawn from the reacting mixture at different stages and analyzed via TEM, SQUID, mass spectrometry (Ms) and UV-Vis.

Figure 5.a shows the evolution of the UV-VIS spectra for samples at different reaction times under standard conditions. These results can be analyzed along with the evolution of the gas phase concentrations of species with mass 28 and 44, obtained from online mass spectrometry during reaction (Figure 5.b), corresponding to the principal decomposition products from the thermolysis of metal acetylacetonates^[46]. UV/Vis spectra recorded at room temperature (RT) revealed the presence of a strong absorption band at about 273 nm and a weak broad band occurring near 350 nm, which were not detected in the UV-VIS spectrum of the pure TEG sample. These peaks were assigned to the transitions bands of the iron (III) acetylacetonate complexes, specifically to the acetylacetonate intraligand transition π - π^* and to the metal-to-ligand charge transfer transitions band, respectively^[47].

Figure 5. Analysis of sample aliquots taken during reaction: a) UV-VIS absorption spectra of sample aliquots extracted at different temperatures and times; b) Mass spectrometry signal as a function of time for $m/z = 44$ and (inset) $m/z = 28$; c) Magnetization curves recorded at 5 K of sample aliquots extracted at different times; Key: St) RT, 0 minute reaction time; N1) 1 minute aging time at 180 °C; N2) 30 minutes aging time at 180 °C; N3) 1 minute aging time at 280 °C; and N4) 30 minutes aging time at 280 °C.

From RT to 180 °C the intensity of the absorption band located at 273 nm started to decrease until it disappeared at temperatures around 280 °C. This behavior was attributed to the decrease in the π - π^* transition energy, as a consequence of the gradual decrease on the metal-acac- π interactions as acetylacetonate groups were progressively removed from the metalorganic precursor $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ complexes to be subsequently decomposed and evaporated from the reactant solution during the heating process^[48]. Finally, an intense and broad absorption band around 220-230 nm was detected in the UV-VIS spectra of sample aliquots drawn from the reaction mixture after 31 minutes at 180 °C (data not shown). Such absorption feature is typical of transition from $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ excited state in glycolaldehyde^[49] or glyoxylic acid^[50], often reported as subproducts during the dehydration and oxidation of heated glycol compounds^[51].

The gaseous products evolved from the $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]/\text{TEG}$ reactant mixture were followed by mass spectrometry and found to be mainly acetaldehyde ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$), CO_2 and CO , in accordance with results reported by *Jasim et al.*^[52] and *Reijnen et al.*^[53] for the thermal decomposition of several metal acetylacetonates. The evolution of the signals corresponding to $m/z = 44$, ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$), and $m/z = 28$ (CO) is shown in figure 5.b. There was no significant gas emission during aging time at 180°C , the main gas emission event started around $240\text{-}250^\circ\text{C}$ and its intensity increased strongly from 280°C . These results were in coincidence with extinction of the transitions bands assigned the iron (III) acetylacetonate complexes in the UV-VIS absorption spectra of the aliquot samples extracted from the reactant mixture between 180°C and 280°C . These results suggest that the thermal decomposition of the free or coordinating acetylacetonate groups requires temperatures above 200°C to occur with a significant rate. The TG profiles of solid $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ (not shown) were in agreement with the above observations, with a strong weight loss (mass decrease of about 76 %) between $\sim 180^\circ\text{C}$ and 280°C .

Figure 5c displays the M - H curves recorded at 5 K for sample aliquots drawn during reaction. These results together with the TEM observations of the same samples shed light on the nucleation and growth processes of iron oxide crystals (see supporting information, figure S5).

As shown in figure 5c, the sample drawn at room temperature presented paramagnetic behavior as expected, due to the Fe (III) ions of the complex. A similar behaviour can also be observed for sample N1 when the reaction temperature reaches 180°C . After aging at 180°C for 30 min (N2) the magnetization is very low but the coercivity of the loop is around 620 Oe suggesting the presence of iron atoms undergoing superexchange

interactions via oxygen, leading to intermediate structures between molecular complexes and small clusters. The high value of coercivity is due to the presence of most of the Fe^{3+} ions on the surface which requires a high energy to align their moments. The coercivity experiments a sharp decrease to 130 Oe when the reaction reaches 280 °C (N3) while the magnetic moment increases somewhat. This diminution of coercivity occurs simultaneously to the decomposition of the remaining acetylacetonate ligands, leading to nuclei with a defined crystalline structure. Finally, during reaction at the reflux temperature the coercivity increases again to 330 Oe, as well as the magnetization. Taking into account that this increase takes place at temperatures where a considerable crystalline growth occurs, it seems likely that the main cause is the increase of the particle and crystalline size: in highly crystalline, small-size particles, magnetocrystalline and shape anisotropy emerged, surface anisotropy was negligible and the coercivity increases again^[54].

The TEM analysis of sample aliquots drawn from the reactant solution (supporting information, figure S5) is coherent with the results of the magnetic measurements: For the aliquot drawn 1 min after the temperature reached 180 °C, TEM micrographs (supporting information, figure S5a) show a population of poorly crystalline particles with a size around 2 nm, and 30 min of further heating at this temperature did not cause significant change (supporting information, figure S5b). Upon heating the reaction mixture to 280 °C (supporting information, figure S5c) iron oxide nuclei form, which under further reaction at this temperature grow to their final size (supporting information, figure S5d).

DISCUSSION

Figure 6 summarizes the effect of the variables studied on the final size of the iron oxide nanoparticles obtained. The above observations on samples taken at different stages of the

process suggest that nanoparticle formation proceeds through a multistep process involving: 1) initial reaction, likely involving the formation of metallo-organic intermediates; 2) reduction of metal complexes by the solvent; 3) decomposition of the complexes leading to the iron oxide precursors; 4) nucleation and final growth of iron oxide nanoparticles. This hypothesis is consistent with the classical model of *LaMer et al.* for the formation of particles in liquids^[55], often quoted to explain the synthesis of metals in a polyol medium^[56-59].

In the present work, the gradual heating of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ dissolved in TEG likely gives rise to the formation of an intermediate alkoxy-acetylacetonate- Fe^{3+} , with Fe ions coordinated to both TEG and acac anions, through an alkylolysis reaction (route 1, scheme 2). This would promote assembling to form large intermediate metal complexes (route 2), where TEG groups could act as bridging ligands allowing polymerization to occur.

The formation of these alkoxy-acetylacetonate- Fe^{3+} complexes which are known to exhibit super-exchange interactions^[60], would be consistent with the color change of the solution from orange to deep red-brown observed in the interval 90 °C -180 °C and also with the considerable reduction on the intensity of the UV-VIS bands located at 273 and 350 nm in the reaction mixture drawn after 11 min at 180 ° C, due to the removal of the acetylacetonate groups from $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$. This change in the UV VIS bands was coincident with the presence of small, low-crystallinity nanoparticles inside the TEG solvent at 180 °C and with the gradual emergence of a ferromagnetic/antiferromagnetic component in the magnetization (Figure 5. N1) compared with the paramagnetic regime of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$.

Figure 6. Summary of the results obtained regarding the effect of process variables on nanoparticle sizes.

A second color change of the reactant solution from deep red to dark was observed after 20 min at 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and after 30 min, a strong reduction of the intensity of the bands at 273 and 350 nm was observed. This change coincided with the generation of glycolaldehyde, as already discussed, a phenomenon already reported for the polyol-mediated synthesis of silver nanostructures^[51] by *Skrabalak et al.* who attributed this phenomenon to the partial transformation of the hot TEG to glycolaldehyde. The presence of glycolaldehyde is important because it is an effective reducing agent for many metal ions, thus adding to the reducing character of TEG. From these observations, it was inferred that, when the reactant solution was kept long enough at 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the decomposition of the acetylacetonate moiety of the metallo-organic intermediate proceeded to an appreciable extent, gradually

unraveling the $(\text{acac})_2\text{Fe-O-TEG}$ complex, and giving rise to measurable changes in the magnetic properties.

Scheme 2. Illustration of the proposed reactions between $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ and TEG molecules

The oxidation potential of TEG is larger than the reduction potential of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} ^[61], indicating that the reduction is thermodynamically unfavorable. As a result, magnetite nanoparticles could only be synthesized at sufficiently high temperatures, when the thermal energy supplied to the system upon heating compensates the energy gap. Thus, prolonged aging at 180 °C was not able to directly generate Fe^{2+} in significant amounts. However, raising the temperature above 240-250 °C led to the thermolysis of the remaining acetylacetonate moiety of the metallo-organic phase, which decomposed into degradation products, acetaldehyde, CO_2 and CO , producing the rapid formation of small iron oxide nuclei. This interpretation is supported by the extinction of the metal-acac- π interactions absorption bands in the UV-VIs at the beginning of the reflux stage, and by the fact that 2 nm iron oxide nanoparticles 2 nm with low coercivity and magnetization could be magnetically isolated from the aliquot sample N3. In this scenario, it is not surprising that

the heating rate used from room temperature to 180°C (β_1), and the extension of the aging period at 180 °C had little or no effect on the final characteristics of the product nanoparticles, as shown in figure 6.

The final step of the reaction (reflux at 280 °C) was characterized by the rapid growth of the iron oxide nuclei from 2 nm to their final size (5 nm and larger) and ripening of the size distribution. The classical *LaMer et al.*^[55] crystallization model predicts that, once the nuclei are formed, the concentration of metal ions is quickly lowered below critical saturation. Under these conditions particle growth occurs on the original nuclei by diffusion from the precursors present in solution. In our work, the main nucleation process occurred during the final temperature ramp, from 180°C to the final reflux temperature, once the temperature reaches values above 240°C. These high temperatures had direct consequences: on the one hand, a higher temperature increased the rate of generation of new iron species through the decomposition of intermediate complexes and of the remaining acetylacetonate. On the other, increasing the temperature had the twofold effect of increasing the kinetics of crystal growth and of facilitating mass transfer to the growing crystals by increasing the diffusion coefficient and reducing the liquid viscosity.

Figure 6 shows that the variables, which had the main influence on the final particle size, were the total iron concentration at the start of the synthesis process and the boiling temperature of the solvent; any increase in the value of these variables consistently led to larger particles, up to a maximum size of 12 nm under the conditions studied. On the other hand, figure 6 also shows that the heating rate from 180°C to the reflux temperature (β_2) had no effect on the final size of the nanoparticles. This was an unexpected result, since in the presence of an extended nucleation process, where secondary nucleation and particle

growth could coexist for a prolonged time, different heating rates would lead to widely different particle size distributions. The fact that this did not happen seems to suggest a rapid nucleation process upon reaching a threshold temperature that quickly relieves supersaturation, effectively suppressing secondary nucleation. In this scenario, any dissolved iron would be quickly incorporated to the growing nanoparticles, thanks to the fast diffusion in the low-viscosity environment provided at the reflux temperatures used.

We have calculated the variation of the viscosity as function of temperature for pure EG, DEG, TEG and TTEG using the software package Aspen Hysys™. The results (data not shown) show a sharp decrease of the viscosity, until values around 2-3 mPa·s reached at 140-150 °C for all solvents, which agrees with experimental measurements of different pure glycols and glycol/water mixtures reported by *Bohne et al.* [62] and Obermier et al. [63]. This strong decrease of viscosity with temperature represents a significant advantage for the solvents with a higher boiling point. Thus, as table 2 shows, TTEG, the solvent with the highest viscosity at room temperature (58.3 mPa·s) presents the lowest viscosity at the boiling temperature (0.009 mPa·s at 315 °C). This low viscosity together with the increase of the diffusion coefficient means that a fast diffusion of dissolved iron species can be expected during the reflux stage with TTEG. The opposite is true for EG, with the lowest viscosity at room temperature (19.1 mPa·s) and the highest during reflux (0.037 mPa·s at 197 °C).

The increase in particle size at the high temperatures afforded by TEG and TTEG solvents can be explained in terms of the high rates of crystal growth and mass transfer reached, meaning that new iron species produced by decomposition of the remaining [Fe(acac)₃] were rapidly sequestered by the growing crystal, rather than accumulate in the solution to

produce secondary nucleation. The same reasoning explains the increase in particle size with higher concentrations of iron in the starting solution. A rapid decomposition would lead to a large number of nuclei, consuming all nutrients to render a large number of small nanoparticles. Instead, in this case the decomposition process was gradual, occurring through intermediate metal-organic complexes that, together with any remaining $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ acted as a reservoir of nutrients that were gradually released to the growing particles.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results presented above, the success of the polyol-based methods in producing a relatively narrow distribution of non-aggregated iron oxide nanoparticles can be explained as the consequence of several concurrent factors. On the one hand, the solvent-reducer environment allowed the partial decomposition of the reactants and the formation of intermediate complexes and low-order aggregates in the first stages of the process: during aging at 180 °C small clusters of iron oxide of a few number of atoms coordinated with acetylacetonate ligands and glycol were formed, while the acetylacetonate ligands started to unbind from the Fe ions. On the other, the high viscosity of the solvent at low and intermediate temperatures created a "solvent cage"-like effect that hindered further aggregation, which means that the individuality of the small clusters can be maintained.

Once the threshold temperature for nucleation was reached, it seems likely that a large proportion of the iron still remained bound in metal-organic complexes or as remaining $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$, from which it was gradually released to be used for particle growth. The high temperatures afforded by the polyol solvents accelerated both the crystal growth and the diffusion of iron species towards the growing crystal, keeping low their concentration in

solution and avoiding further nucleation. As a consequence, the particle size of the iron oxide nanoparticles can be controlled by two main process variables: the total $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ concentration and the type of solvent used.

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ASSOCIATED CONTENT:

Supporting information. 1) TEM images of TEG-SPIONs samples synthesized by using different heating rate to heat from 25 °C to 280 °C and by using different aging at 180 °C at 280 °C. 2) TEM micrographs of sample aliquots extracted from the reaction at different reaction time. This material is available free of charge via internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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TABLE CAPTIONS:

Table 1. Physical parameters studied and modified values compared to the standard synthesis. Data in bold type represents standard synthesis parameters.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the solvents used. * Calculated using chemical engineering software Aspen Hysys™ v7.0.

SCHEME CAPTIONS:

Scheme 1. Main stages and parameters in the synthesis process.

Scheme 2. Illustration of the proposed reactions between $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$ and TEG molecules

FIGURE CAPTIONS:

Figure 1. Structural Characterization of TEG-coated iron oxide particles obtained under standard conditions: a) XRD pattern (the reflections of Fe_3O_4 were included for comparison); b) TEM micrograph of iron oxide nanoparticles; c) Particle size distribution calculated from analysis of TEM images (lognormal curve fitting) and d) Lattice plane fringes and Fourier transform of the indicated zone of the particles.

Figure 2. TEM images and particle size distributions of iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized using different amount of $[\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3]$: a) 0.05 g, b) 0.2 g, c) 0.4 g, d) 1.3 g, e) 2 g and f) 3 g.

- Figure 3. TEM pictures and particle size distributions of iron oxide nanoparticles using different solvents: a) EG b) DEG c) TEG d) TTEG e) 1:1 vol/vol TEG/TOA and f) 1:1 vol/vol TEG/TOPO mixture.
- Figure 4. TEM images of TEG-coated SPIONs obtained by solvothermally synthesis with aging time of 30 min; b) Same as sample (a) but using aging time 5 h; c) TEM picture of particles obtained using standard conditions; d) XRD patterns of solvothermally synthesized particles, aging time 30 min (reference of bulk magnetite and iron oxide nanoparticles obtained using standard conditions are included for comparison).
- Figure 5. Analysis of the sample aliquots taken during the reaction: a) UV-VIs absorption spectra of samples aliquots extracted at different temperatures and times; b) Mass spectrometry signal as a function of time for $m/z = 44$ and (inset) $m/z = 28$; c) Magnetization curves recorded at 5 K of sample aliquots extracted at different times; Key: St) RT, 0 min reaction time; N1) 1 minute aging time at 180° C; N2) 30 minutes aging time at 180 °C; N3) 1 minute aging time at 280 °C; and N4) 30 minutes aging time at 280 °C.
- Figure 6. Summary of the results obtained regarding the effect of process variables on nanoparticle sizes.